

Evaluation of the VirtualSpeech Course Component of the Art of Applying Psychology 2024

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Background

This report evaluates the implementation of a course component that involved presenting in virtual reality. This component was part of the course the Art of Applying Psychology (AOAP), which is one of the mandatory courses of the master's specialization in Applied Cognitive Psychology at Leiden University. In this course, students are divided into teams which are given the task to develop a business idea based on scientific research in the cognitive psychology field. The teams consist of several different members focusing on all aspects needed to develop a new product such as research, finance, and management. Each team is led by a CEO and a vice-CEO (from now on simply CEOs). At the beginning of the course, the students present their idea to their class and the teachers through a quick pitch and at the end of the course students present their developed business plan to a team of investors. To aid the students in these presentation efforts and to enable them to develop their presentation skills more generally, part of the course was to practice these presentations in the VR software VirtualSpeech. This software allows users to practice presenting in a real-life situation in VR. Users can choose between different types of rooms to practice in, such as a small board room or a larger lecture room. The software records and analyzes the presentation by tracking speech, gestures, and movement and provides detailed feedback based on this analysis. VirtualSpeech allows the users to use uploaded slides and notes while presenting and the software contains interesting features such as audience questions by generative artificial intelligence based on the presentation content.

In 2023, students of AOAP also used VirtualSpeech for the same purpose. However, as a pilot and was only mandatory for the CEOs of each team while it was voluntary for other members. Following the VR presentation component in 2023, the feedback of the participants ($n = 9$) led to the full implementation of this component again in the current year. This year, the VR

component is mandatory for each student and consists of two sessions for each student to practice presenting in VR in the labs of the Faculty of Social Sciences. All non-CEOs were supposed to present the product pitch of their team in the second and fourth week of the course, while the CEOs presented the final product presentation in the sixth and seventh week as a preparation for their dragon's den presentation for the investors. The current report evaluates the full implementation of the VirtualSpeech course component by reporting on the feedback given by the students and the experimenter and the speech analysis done by the software.

Methods

Participants

All students ($n = 20$) from the course the Art of Applying Psychology were instructed to participate in two 30-minute individual VR sessions where they practiced their presentations in VirtualSpeech. Due to issues with the license of the VR software in the second week of the course, three students could not participate in their first session. Furthermore, two participants reported having nothing to present upon arrival in their first session and left without having presented. Finally, one student did not register for their second session in week 4 and therefore only practiced once. This makes the total sample size of students who practiced twice $n = 14$.

Materials

For this course component two Meta Quest 3 VR headsets were used and the software VirtualSpeech. The VirtualSpeech software has recently expanded its functionalities, which were offered as optional to the students. As a result, some of these were used by some but not all students. The option to have distractions entails sounds, noises, and people in the audience

interrupting the speaker. After a couple of students tried this option, it became clear that this was too much of a distraction as the audience kept interrupting the speaker, asking repetitive questions, as well as the sounds being too intense and unrealistic, so this option was then no longer used. The option to see live feedback entails gaining feedback by the software to make more eye contact with certain parts of the room or adjust speaking volume and tempo. This option was recommended to all participants and was working well. All participants were instructed to use a room type, which was the board room for all non-CEOs and the conference room for CEOs. These rooms were chosen to best represent the presentation scenario for their roles, which are presenting for stakeholders of a business team for non-CEOs and a panel of investors with audience for CEOs. All non-CEOs using the board room were instructed to use the option with a large audience, which fills up the entire board room with avatars. Lastly, the option to watch one's presentation back from the audience was not recommended but still used by some participants who had time left in the VR session, but it was not liked by the students.

Procedure

Before the first session, students were instructed through the online learning environment to create their VirtualSpeech account. Upon arrival at the lab, they were instructed on how to upload their slides from their own device so that they could access these in the VR application. Next, students filled in the first part of a questionnaire, while the experimenter logged the participants in on the headset. The first part of the questionnaire consisted of two subparts; a subjective evaluation of nine general soft skills rated on a 5-point likert scale and one question asking which soft skill students wanted to improve. After this question the participants were given the VR headset and controllers, and the headsets were adjusted to each student's preference. Students were instructed on how to use the VR software and hardware and were told

to navigate to the VR presentation room corresponding to their role. When the students were done presenting, they received an evaluation of their presentation in the VR software. Next, the experimenter instructed the students to proceed with answering AI generated questions based on their presentation. Once the students had read the feedback and answered the AI generated questions they were told to save and upload their presentation and feedback. After completing the VR session, the participants completed the second part of the questionnaire which asked them about which features of VirtualSpeech they found helpful, if VirtualSpeech improved their skills and confidence, the value of VirtualSpeech in the course and additional feedback. Additionally, the experimenter asked them more informally what they thought of the experience to gain some more insight into the students' experiences.

Results

This section contains results of the questionnaires as completed by the participants of the VR sessions. The results follow the same order as the order of the questions mentioned earlier.

Quantitative results soft skills

Figure 1 to Figure 8 show the distribution of responses to the first part of the questionnaire focused on the soft skills of the participants.

Figure 1

Score distribution of “How would you rate your communication skills?”

Figure 2

Score distribution of “How would you rate your presentation skills?”

Figure 3

Score distribution of “How would you rate your leadership skills?”

Figure 4

Score distribution of “How would you rate your active listening skills?”

Figure 5

Score distribution of “How would you rate your negotiation skills?”

Figure 6

Score distribution of “How would you rate your networking skills?”

Figure 7

Score distribution of “How would you rate your connection with colleagues?”

Figure 8

Pie chart with responses to “Which soft skills would you like to improve?”

Speech Analysis by Virtual Speech

The Virtual Speech software conducts a meticulous analysis of a participant's presentation skills. Besides an overall presentation score with a grade between 0 and 1, the app also provides detailed written feedback and scores on eye contact, speaking pace (words per minute), the percentage of filler words (words such as uhm) relative to normal words, listenability, body language, and content score. This section is dedicated to some of the results from this speech analysis. Figure 9 demonstrates the progression in overall scores between the first and the second session of each participant. As the figure shows, there was no clear improvement or worsening of the scores. Half of the participants scored higher in the second session and half of the participants scored lower relative to the first session, although the differences were marginal most of the time. In general, we can observe a very slight decrease in overall presentation scores.

Figure 9

Line plot displaying the progression of overall presentation scores between sessions

Note: The different colored lines represent different participants while the thick black line represents the average of all colored lines

Figure 10

Line plot displaying the progression of using filler words relative to all words between sessions

Note: The different colored lines represent different participants while the thick black line represents the average of all colored lines

Figure 10 displays the progression of the amount of filler words between the two sessions, with most participants showing a slight decrease in the percentage of filler words, as well as a slight average decrease. Similarly, Figure 11 shows a slight decrease in words per minute, listenability score, and body language score, although most differences seem negligible. Note that most participants were in both sessions at the by VirtualSpeech recommended speaking pace of 100-150 words per minute. The scores of eye contact have been omitted from the results due to a great amount of users reporting that they had eye contact scores of or near zero, even when they purposefully sought to increase their eye contact with the audience.

Figure 11

Several line plots displaying the progression of A) words per minute, B) listenability score, and C) body language score between the two sessions.

Participant feedback

This section shows an overview of the results of the questions asking students to evaluate the use of Virtualspeech. Figures 12 to 14 show the quantitative responses to a couple of questions and are followed by a section providing an overview of qualitative feedback.

Figure 12

Distribution of responses to “Do you think your skills have improved on VirtualSpeech?”

Figure 13

Distribution of responses to “Do you think your confidence to use your skills has increased with VirtualSpeech?”

Figure 14

Distribution of answers to the question “Do you think VirtualSpeech is a useful addition to your learning offering?”

Qualitative Feedback

The feedback provided in response to the question "Any other feedback? (Please share below)" offered valuable qualitative insights into participants' experiences with the VirtualSpeech software. Additionally, the experimenter has gained oral feedback from the participants surrounding the VirtualSpeech sessions. This section summarizes key themes and highlights common suggestions and sentiments expressed by users.

Overall experience of the VR course component

All participants reported that they liked presenting in VR and that they saw the value in this course component. Several users remarked that they saw the benefit of practicing presenting in VR and that they would like to do this more often for presentations. The users even expressed that they considered themselves lucky to get this opportunity, which was especially the case for the CEOs as they were practicing for the high-stakes dragon's den presentation for the panel of investors. There were also a couple of users who expressed the usefulness of this tool given their performance anxiety and fear of presenting. Users appreciated the immersive nature of the software, especially the realistic virtual environments that helped them practice public speaking skills in a comfortable yet challenging way. The users highlighted that the interactive elements contributed significantly to their overall learning experience. In general, participants gave feedback that the VirtualSpeech platform was easy to use and engaging, seeing it as a highly valuable tool.

Despite positive comments, some users suggested areas for improvement. To begin with, there was quite some confusion surrounding the course set up related to the VR component. Non-CEOs were supposed to practice in VR already in week 2 but by then the roles were not

clear yet and to a large amount of people who signed up this week it was not clear what they had to present. As a result, there were a handful of participants who could not adequately participate in the first sessions. There were also many users in week 2 and in week 4 for who it felt like they just came to the VR session as it was mandatory and lacked having something important to practice presenting. Furthermore, because of the confusion regarding the course set up people who signed up for week 2 who became CEO afterwards had to come again in the weeks dedicated to CEO presentations or had to cancel their sign up for this first week of VR presenting.

Although the received feedback was seen as helpful, multiple participants said they would have liked to practice the same presentation again in the same session, so that they could apply the received feedback immediately. A common theme was the desire for more diverse scenarios or more varied practice environments. A few users expressed the desire to have more insight into the scores calculated for them as not every calculated score was accompanied by additional motivation. Besides, the non-CEOs were instructed by the course organizers to practice presenting in a board room for a small audience as this fitted their roles the most, while they had preferred presenting in a bigger room as this is a more challenging scenario harder to find in real life.

Technical Aspects

Users provided feedback on several technical aspects of VirtualSpeech, highlighting both platform-specific issues and realism concerns. The technical challenges included lag during exercises and unresponsive interactive features.

A handful of users provided feedback on technical issues. These included minor glitches such as lag during specific exercises, or difficulties with the responsiveness of some interactive features. Users also reported that, although VirtualSpeech offers a nice practicing environment, the technology makes the experience a bit unrealistic at times. For example, the avatars are nodding all the time instead of relatedly to what is spoken, do not look realistic, or were reported to have unrealistic faces and eyes. The feature of distractions during the presentation is supposed to make presenting more realistic as in real life people will be distracted too, but as they were so overly exaggerated it hampered the realistic aspect of the experience. Users often indicated that they often felt like the scores on body language and eye contact were not representative of their actual presenting behavior. Many people reported receiving scores of 0 on eye contact even when purposefully trying to increase eye contact. Lastly, there had been an issue with the license of the software during the course which caused several people in week 2 not being able to participate, which made them participate only once. The software said that the license code was used too many times while only a quarter of all students had participated (and only for the first session) which then had to be resolved with VirtualSpeech.

Discussion

The VirtualSpeech component in the Art of Applying Psychology course has shown substantial value in helping students improve presentation skills in a realistic, immersive setting. Participants responded positively, noting the opportunity to practice in VR as unique and beneficial, especially for those with presentation anxiety or preparing for high-stakes events. Many viewed the tool as an excellent resource for enhancing public speaking performance and

building confidence, with VR allowing them to practice in challenging yet controlled environments.

However, the scores based on the speech analysis do not show clear changes between the sessions which shows that people might not have been able to implement the received feedback and improve their presenting skills. This might have to do with a lack of relevance and importance for practicing presenting for the non-CEOs. Early confusion around participant roles led to ineffective initial sessions for some, as unclear instructions prevented full engagement. Besides, many participants did not have anything pressing to present. However, if this were true we would expect that the CEOs should see a progression between the two sessions which is also not the case. For future iterations, clearer guidelines and role assignments at the course outset would better prepare students, maximizing the potential of each VR session. In general, it is doubtful in whether a clear progress can be made between the first and second session as higher presentation scores in the second relative to the first session only occurred for a half of the participants and were very marginal increases in most cases.

Technical limitations were another recurring theme. Participants experienced occasional lag and unresponsiveness in VR, along with unrealistic avatars and exaggerated audience distractions, which sometimes detracted from the immersion. Additionally, inconsistencies in scoring for eye contact and body language left some participants uncertain about how to interpret their feedback. Addressing these issues through refined technology and user guidance could make VirtualSpeech an even more effective and realistic training tool, creating a seamless and engaging experience that fully supports students in developing their presentation skills.

Given the reported limitations on several presentation metrics and the fact that no clear result can be found, it is not possible to conclude on the validity of the presentation scores given

by VirtualSpeech. However, inferring from the qualitative feedback it is possible to conclude that the current course component is a useful addition.